

Statistical Analysis Plan

Mesh placement and patient-reported outcomes in primary ventral hernia repair

Version 1.0

Usamah Ahmed, MD¹

Hugin Reistrup, MD, PhD¹

Anders Gram-Hanssen, MD, PhD¹

Jacob Rosenberg, MD, DMSc¹

Laus Wolsing Wullum, MSc²

Jason Joe Baker, MD, PhD¹

¹ Center for Perioperative Optimization, Department of Surgery, Copenhagen University Hospital - Herlev and Gentofte, Borgmester Ib Juuls Vej 1, DK-2730 Herlev, Denmark

² Sanos Group ApS, Telefonvej 8D, DK-2860 Søborg, Denmark

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INTRODUCTION

This statistical analysis plan describes the statistical and data-related aspects of a planned register-based observational cohort study that includes data from a nationwide survey. The study will investigate different mesh placements in primary ventral hernia repair and their impact on patient-reported outcomes (PROs), including chronic pain and foreign body sensation. The data come from a nationwide Danish cohort of patients who had surgery for primary ventral hernia between January 1, 2014, and March 31, 2024. PROs are based on the Abdominal Hernia-Q (AHQ), which is a validated questionnaire for patients who have undergone ventral hernia repair [1]. The AHQ includes questions about pain, foreign body sensation, activities of daily living, quality of life, and satisfaction.

ANALYSIS OBJECTIVES

Primary objective

To investigate the association between mesh placement and PROs (AHQ sum score) in adults undergoing elective primary ventral hernia repair.

Secondary objectives

To investigate the prevalence severe chronic pain and foreign body sensation according to mesh placement.

STUDY METHODS

This study will use data from the AFTERHERNIA Project [2], the Danish Ventral Hernia Database [3], and the Danish Register of Authorized Health Personnel [4]. In the AFTERHERNIA Project, patients were identified through the Danish National Patient Register [5] and linked with the Danish Civil Registration System [6]. This allowed them to receive a questionnaire asking about details such as PROs, including severe pain, foreign body sensation, and lifestyle factors. These questionnaire responses were then linked to data from the Danish Ventral Hernia Database [3]. The Danish Ventral Hernia Database contains perioperative details, such as date of surgery, type of mesh used, mesh placement, mesh fixation technique, hernia defect size, surgical approach (open, laparoscopic, or robotic), whether the procedure was acute or elective, and patient characteristics including sex and age [7]. Data from the Danish Ventral Hernia Database were provided by the

Danish Healthcare Quality Institute, which also supplied information from the Danish National Patient Register. Additionally, a register-based Charlson Comorbidity Index was included [8], derived from hospital diagnoses recorded in the Danish National Patient Register.

PROs are based on the AHQ, a questionnaire developed for patients who have undergone ventral hernia repair [1]. The AHQ includes both preoperative and postoperative versions; for this study, only the postoperative version was used. The AHQ has been validated in Danish [9]. The AHQ covers seven domains: (1) expectations, (2) self and others, (3) surgeon and surgical team, (4) sensation, (5) function, (6) appearance, and (7) overall satisfaction [1]. It consists of 16 items in total. Each item is scored on a 4-point Likert scale. The AHQ sum score is calculated by simply adding the item scores, with no weighting or transformation. The total score ranges from 16 to 64 points, where 64 represents the best outcome and 16 the worst.

All patients who underwent elective primary ventral hernia repair (defined as umbilical or epigastric) between January 1, 2014, and March 31, 2024, were assessed for eligibility. Each patient was included only once.

ANALYSIS POPULATION, TYPE OF ANALYSIS

Analysis population

A flowchart of data selection is shown in Figure 1.

Inclusion criteria:

- Adult patients ≥ 18 years old
- Elective primary ventral hernia (umbilical and epigastric) repair in Denmark between January 1, 2014, and March 31, 2024
- Hernia defect width < 10 cm
- Operation with insertion of mesh
 - Onlay
 - Retromuscular
 - Preperitoneal
 - Intraperitoneal

Exclusion criteria:

- Operation not registered in the Danish Ventral Hernia Database, as data of mesh placement will be missing
- Reoperation for recurrence
- Emergency repairs
- Other hernias
- Other mesh placement
- Hernias repaired without mesh
- If component separation had been performed
- Deceased and emigrated patients
- Lack of Danish language skills
- Cognitive deficit (e.g., dementia)
- Physical handicap (e.g., blindness, paralysis)
- Participant not feeling able to answer (e.g., due to other illness)
- Participants exempt from using Digital Post
- Follow-up < 6 months
- Non-disclosure of address
- Participants who answered 'no' to the screening question about having had ventral hernia surgery.

Covariates and stratum

As this is an observational study, analyses will be adjusted for the following potential and predefined confounders:

1. Age (continuous variable)
2. Sex (binary variable)
3. Hernia defect width in cm (continuous variable)
4. Charlson Comorbidity Index (categorical variable, five levels: 0, 1, 2, 3, ≥ 4)
 - Patients with a score of 4 or higher will be grouped into a single category
 - This categorization is based on prior analyses from the Danish Ventral Hernia Database, which indicate that the number of patients with scores above 4 is limited, thus necessitating grouping for analytical robustness
5. BMI (categorical: <18.5; 18.5-24.9; 25-29.9; 30-34.9; 35-39.9; ≥ 40)
6. Smoking status (categorical: yes, no, previous)
7. Follow up, years (continuous)

Subgroups

- Hernia defect widths: small (≤ 1 cm), medium (>1 to ≤ 4 cm), and large (>4 to <10 cm)
- Surgical approach: open, laparoscopic, and robot-assisted

HANDLING OF MISSING VALUES

Analyses will be done using complete cases without imputation for missing covariates.

STATISTICAL METHODOLOGY

Demography and patient characteristics

Patient characteristics will be summarized descriptively by mesh placement. Categorical variables will be presented as counts and percentages, and continuous variables as medians with interquartile ranges.

Primary endpoints

The primary outcome of interest is the AHQ sum score.

The primary outcome will be analyzed using linear regression models adjusted for covariates specified in the "Covariates" section of this statistical analysis plan. Standardization (g-computation) will be applied to account for confounding and estimate marginal means. Results will be reported as marginal mean AHQ sum scores and mean differences by mesh placement, with onlay serving as the reference group. Estimates will be reported with 95% confidence intervals and corresponding p-values. All hypotheses will be tested at a two-sided significance level of 5%.

Secondary endpoints

Secondary endpoints include differences in rates of chronic pain and foreign body sensation. These outcomes will be treated as binary variables (yes/no), where a response level of 4 indicates "no," and responses ranging from 1 to 3 indicate "yes."

Analyses will be conducted using logistic regression models adjusted for the same covariates as in the primary analysis. Standardization will be used to estimate marginal prevalence and prevalence differences across mesh placements. Results will be reported as marginal prevalence estimates and prevalence differences by mesh placement, using onlay as the reference group. Estimates will

include 95% confidence intervals and corresponding p-values. All hypotheses will be tested at a two-sided significance level of 5%.

ADDITIONAL ANALYSES

Sensitivity analyses

- Removal of items 3a, 4a, 5a, 6a, 7a from the AHQ sum score
 - Domains Surgical Team and Preparedness are not considered to be influenced by, or to have an impact on, mesh placement.
- Removal of self-reported recurrence
 - Recurrence can cause pain, foreign body sensation, functional problems, affect self-image, etc. By excluding patients who have had a recurrence in a sensitivity analysis, we can ensure that the PRO is due to the surgery and not the recurrence
- Removal of Physiomesh™
 - Physiomesh™ was associated with increased recurrence rates [10]
- Specialist
 - Specialist, yes
 - Specialist, no
 - Specialist, no, supervised
- Only IPOM+ (technique with intraperitoneal mesh and closure of defect with suture) [11]
 - Exclusion of regular IPOM (with no defect closure)
- If greater variations exist in Table 1 that theoretically could influence the outcomes, we will test for this in a sensitivity analysis
- Inverse probability weighting (IPW) analysis
 - To assess potential model misspecification, an IPW analysis will be performed targeting the same estimand as the primary analysis. Propensity scores will be fitted using logistic regression with the same covariates as in the primary model.

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Figures

Figure 1: Flowchart of data selection and collection process

DVHD, Danish Ventral Hernia Database; IPOM, intraperitoneal onlay mesh.